

**THE STYLISTIC CONSTRUCTION OF THE GOTHIC IN MARY SHELLEY'S
"FRANKENSTEIN"**Scientific supervisor: **Asqarova Shakhnoza Kamolidinovna**

Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies

Master's degree student **Qurbonova Umida Begaliyevna**

Telephone number: +998881113135

E-mail: umidaqurbonova71@gmail.com**Annotation**

This article examines Mary Shelley's "Frankenstein" from a linguocultural perspective, focusing on the connection between language, culture, and Gothic elements with Romantic ideals. The work analyzes how landscape descriptions, metaphors, and irony mirror the nineteenth-century cultural values and moral responsibility. In particular, attention to nature symbolizes both the outer and inner worlds of the characters enhancing the Gothic atmosphere of the novel. The research concludes that linguistic choices in Frankenstein are inseparably linked with cultural and ethical concern, especially those related to science, responsibility, and humanity.

Key words

linguocultural analysis, Gothic literature, irony, metaphors, Frankenstein, Romanticism, culture.

Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada Mary Shelley'ning "Frankenstein" asari lingvomadaniy nuqtai nazardan tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda til, madaniyat va gotik unsurlar o'rtasidagi uzviy bog'liqlik yoritiladi. Asarda tabiat tasvirlari, metaforalar va kinoyaning XIX asr madaniy qarashlari hamda romantik g'oyalarni aks ettirishi tahlil qilinadi. Tabiat obrazlari qahramonlarning ichki ruhiy holatini ifodalab, asarning gotik muhitini kuchaytirishi ko'rsatib beriladi. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, asardagi til birliklari ilm-fan, mas'uliyat va insoniylik bilan bog'liq madaniy va axloqiy masalalar bilan chambarchas bog'langan.

Kalit so'zlar

lingvomadaniy tahlil, gotik adabiyot, kinoya, metafora, Frankenstein, romantizm, madaniyat.

Аннотация

В данной статье роман Мэри Шелли «Франкенштейн» рассматривается с лингвокультурологической точки зрения. Анализ направлен на выявление взаимосвязи

языка, культуры и готических элементов произведения. Особое внимание уделяется описаниям природы, метафорам и иронии, которые отражают культурные ценности XIX века и идеи романтизма. Пейзажные образы служат средством выражения внутреннего мира персонажей и усиливают готическую атмосферу романа. Исследование показывает, что языковые средства в Франкенштейне неразрывно связаны с культурными и этическими проблемами науки, ответственности и человечности.

Ключевые слова

лингвокультурологический анализ, готическая литература, ирония, метафора, Франкенштейн, романтизм, культура.

INTRODUCTION

“*Frankenstein; or, The Modern Prometheus*” (1818) by Mary Shelley plays a significant role in English literary history, as the book is regarded as one of the first novels to engage both Romantic and Gothic elements by a female writer. “Emerging at the moment of transition from Romanticism to the Victorian age, the work reflects the very nineteenth-century views, which revolve between individual feelings, imagination, freedom, and social issues, moral values, and scientific responsibilities”¹. The novel has become an extensive research subject for scholars because of its approach to Gothic, Romantic, philosophical, feminist², and cultural perspectives, highlighting its engagement with ambition, science, monstrosity, and modernity³. The study involves M. H. Abrams, focusing on Romantic aspects, while Fred Botting and David Punter analyzed the Gothic literary tradition; however, scholars such as Chris Baldick and Anne K. Mellor approach “Frankenstein” as a critique of science, modernity, and power. Unfortunately, fewer studies address linguistic aspects: how language functions as a tool for portraying a novel’s narrative architecture, symbolic systems, and ideological orientation. This study seeks to fill this gap by employing an integrated stylistic and linguocultural approach within the context of early nineteenth-century modernity, employing linguocultural analysis, text-based methods, with a focus on linguistic, stylistic, and cultural analysis.

In literary studies, linguocultural analysis – an interdisciplinary approach that blends linguistics, culture, and literature is a useful tool. It examines language as a vehicle for cultural identity, showing how linguistic elements convey societal standards, cultural values, and beliefs. Linguocultural analysis can uncover cultural values and beliefs embedded in language, which is a key advantage. Idioms, metaphors, and cultural symbols that are often unique to

¹ Botting, F. *Gothic*. – London: Routledge, 2013. – P. 23.

² Kapuševska-Drakulevska, L. The Frankenstein Complex or The Disturbing Otherness // *English Studies at the Interface of Disciplines: Research and Practice (ESIDRP)*. – 201 – P. 67.

³ Waham, J. J. The Art of Gothic Literature: An Analysis of Mary Shelley’s *Frankenstein* // *International Linguistics Research*. – 2023. – Vol. 6, № 2. – P. 1.

certain communities are stored in language. These linguistic elements are essential to the Gothic genre's atmosphere of mystery and terror⁴.

In Mary Shelley's "Frankenstein", the language is used in a certain way so that it blends both cultural and literary styles. The novel was written during the Industrial Revolution, a period that valued scientific progress rather than morality and social norms. The novel addresses themes such as science and ethics, humanity, creativity, and responsibility, which were central to Western cultural thought at the time.

The novel starts with letters from Robert Walton to his sister, providing a first-person perspective into exploration. Having made use of extensive letters, the author shows the nineteenth-century epistolary tradition, which reflects personal and social documentation of the given period.

Shelley used both complex and descriptive English, employing emotional and dramatic language: "I beheld the wretch – the miserable monster whom I had created"⁵ This sentence alone shows Victor's emotional state and his guilt in creating the monster.

This tone of the language is also used to create a dark, eerie atmosphere, which is typical for Gothic literature: "The cold stars shone in mockery, and the bare trees waved their branches like arms"⁶. In this sentence, Romanticism and the Gothic blend perfectly: while the imaginary reflects the nineteenth-century Romantic fascination with nature and human emotions, the setting evokes an uncomfortable sense, disturbance, fear, and the sublime, which are Gothic elements.

When it comes to Creature, it embodies both cultural anxieties and Gothic horror: "I am malicious because I am miserable"⁷. From a linguocultural perspective, this illustrates societal influence on identity and morality, showing cultural values of irresponsibility and social neglect. His grotesque appearance and emotional intensity blend and generate fear and sympathy together, creating a Gothic characterization.

Irony and Metaphors. Mary Shelley wrote extensively on irony and metaphors in "Frankenstein" to enrich the novel's moral, psychological, and linguocultural aspects.

Irony is seen in Victor's desire and pursuit of knowledge. He strongly believed that his scientific creature would bring humanity benefit, yet it only caused destruction. He wanted to create a life from the dead; however, in the end, it only resulted in the death of his close people, including himself, creating dramatic irony.

⁴ Makhmudov, K. The Importance of Linguocultural Analysis in the Gothic Style // *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*. – 2024. – Vol. 6, № 2. – P. 12–18.

⁵ Shelley, M. *Frankenstein; or, The Modern Prometheus*. – London: Penguin Classics, 1818/1831. – P. 46.

⁶ Shelley, M. *Frankenstein; or, The Modern Prometheus*. – London: Penguin Classics, 1818/1831. – P. 46.

⁷ That source. P. 131.

Another irony can be seen from the perspective of the Creature. Even though he is conventionally unattractive or regarded as monstrous, he displayed sensitivity, intelligence, and moral awareness that belong to human beings. Despite that, many people behave cruelly or selfishly towards him, without knowing his true colours. This situational irony challenged the idea of cultural assumptions about appearance, morality, and humanity in society.

The author also used some metaphors in the text to deepen the meaning. The Creature can be interpreted as a metaphor for social neglect or irresponsibility for the consequences, showing that the dangers of what could happen if not supervised. Victor has references to light and fire throughout the book; these two are shown as knowledge and discovery. While light traditionally symbolizes enlightenment, in “Frankenstein”, it also comes with destruction, reflecting the double-edged nature of scientific progress.

One of the notable remarks is for the landscape descriptions. Nature itself serves as a metaphor. Throughout the text, Shelley used rich vocabulary in describing the surroundings of the main characters. These surroundings also played a huge role in not only giving cultural ideas but also reflecting the inner world of the characters. Nature in “Frankenstein” functions as a symbolic and emotional mirror, where mountains, storms, and desolate landscapes express fear, isolation, and psychological conflict. This use of natural imagery reflects Romantic cultural values that viewed nature as a powerful force connected to human emotion, while also contributing to the Gothic atmosphere of the novel by creating a sense of sublimity and tension⁸.

CONCLUSION

“Frankenstein” is a rich literary work in which language, culture, and literary techniques are intrinsically connected. Through linguocultural aspects, Gothic and Romantic elements, irony, and metaphors, the author reveals moral and cultural concerns of the early nineteenth century. Landscape descriptions, symbolism, and emotional intensity serve not only as Gothic elements but also Romantic ideals, simultaneously representing both outer and inner worlds of the characters. Irony mirrored the consequences of uncontrolled ambition, while metaphors enriched the novel’s exploration of science, responsibility, and humanity. Therefore, “Frankenstein” remains a remarkable novel that represents how linguistic choices can convey cultural values and timeless moral questions.

REFERENCES:

1. Bakhtin, M. M. *The dialogic imagination: Four essays*. – Austin: University of Texas Press, 1982. – 444 p.
2. Baldick, C. *In Frankenstein's shadow: Myth, monstrosity, and nineteenth-century writing*. – Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1990. – 228 p.
3. Botting, F. *Gothic*. – London: Routledge, 2013. – 200 p.
4. Butler, M. *Romantics, rebels, and reactionaries*. – Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1981. – 241 p.
5. Khodjamkulov, U., Makhmudov, K., Abduramanova, D., Ruzmetova, D., Akhatov, L., Djabbarova, F. Exploring Gothic-Themed Lexemes and Their Cultural Connotations in

⁸ Waham, J. J. The Art of Gothic Literature: An Analysis of Mary Shelley’s *Frankenstein* // *International Linguistics Research*. – 2023. – Vol. 6, № 2. – P. 1.

English and Uzbek: An Educational Perspective // *International Journal of Language Education*. – 2024. – Vol. 8, № 4. – 655–677 p.

6. Kapuševska-Drakulevska, L. The Frankenstein Complex or The Disturbing Otherness // *English Studies at the Interface of Disciplines: Research and Practice (ESIDRP)*. – 67–72 p.

7. Makhmudov, K. The Importance of Linguocultural Analysis in the Gothic Style // *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*. – 2024. – Vol. 6, № 2. – 12–18 p.

8. Makhmudov, K., Khodjamkulov, U., Saitkulova, N., Khaldarchaeva, G., Baisov, A., Babadjanova, N. Linguocultural Analysis of Gothic Lexemes and Female Identity in *Dahshat* and *The Yellow Wallpaper*: A Cross-Cultural Study Toward Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) // *International Journal of Language Education*. – 2025. – Т. 9. – № 1. – С. 195–211.

9. Mellor, A. K. A feminist critique of science // *Frankenstein: Mary Shelley* / ed. by Fred. – 1995. – URL: <https://www.researchgate.net> (дата обращения: 12.12.2025).

10. Mellor, A. K. *Mary Shelley: Her life, her fiction, her monsters*. – London: Routledge, 1989. – 300 p.

11. O'Sullivan, J., et al. Did Mary Shelley write *Frankenstein*? A stylometric analysis // *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities*. – 2022. – Vol. 38, № 2. – 750–775 p. – DOI: 10.1093/lc/fqad012.

12. Shelley, M. *Frankenstein; or, The Modern Prometheus*. – London: Lackington, Hughes, Harding, Mavor & Jones, 1818. – 280 p.

13. Waham, J. J. The Art of Gothic Literature: An Analysis of Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein* // *International Linguistics Research*. – 2023. – Vol. 6, № 2. – 1–7 p.

